

Hypergeometric DE Applied to the Time-Dependent Schrodinger Equation

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In a series of notes (1), the wavefunction of the time-independent Schrodinger equation $W(x)$ is written as $W_0(x)W_1(x)$, where $W_0(x)$ is the ground state solution, and:

$$-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W_1(x) - \frac{1}{m} \left(\frac{d}{dx} W_1 \right) \left(\frac{d}{dx} W_0 / W_0 \right) = (E - E_0) W_1(x) \quad ((1))$$

Equation ((1)) is then compared to the hypergeometric form from (2):

$$p(x) \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W(x) + q(x) \frac{d}{dx} W(x) + \text{constant} W(x) = 0 \quad ((2))$$

Where $p(x)$ is at most quadratic in x and $q(x)$ linear. Equation ((2)) has solutions in the form of Rodrigues polynomials given in (2). In this note, we wish to examine the time dependent Schrodinger equation:

$$i \frac{d}{dt} W(x,t) = -\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W(x,t) + V(x,t) W(x,t) \quad ((3))$$

We would like to again use a form similar to ((1)), but this means the time-dependent Schrodinger equation should be converted, through the transformation $g(y)=x+b(t)$, into an equation in y which has the appearance of the time independent Schrodinger equation. This approach has been presented in (3) and (4) for a specific potential $V(x,t) = .5k x^2 + f(t) x$. Here, we wish to find a general method which may be linked to ((1)) and the hypergeometric equation. From this, one may find potentials $V(x,t)$ which yield Rodrigues polynomial solutions.

Transforming the Time-Dependent Schrodinger

We consider using independent variables $y(x,t)$ and t as in (3), but instead of only considering a linear transformation: $y=x-b(t)$, we use:

$$g(y) = x - b(t) \quad ((4))$$

The goal is to write $W(x,t)$ as $W(y)$ multiplied by $\exp(i \text{ quantity})$ factors with all time dependent coefficients disappearing. From there, one may easily obtain an equation similar to ((1)) by writing $W(y) = W_0(y)W_1(y)$.

Let us write a factor: $\exp[i q(y) \frac{d}{dt} b(t)]$. Then (as argued in (4)), we wish to have time flux $\frac{d}{dt} W$ cancel with the spatial flux $\frac{d}{dx} W$ because we assume $W(y)$ is a real function.

$$i \frac{d}{dt} W(y) \frac{dy}{dt} = -i \left(\frac{d}{dt} b \right) / g' \frac{d}{dy} W \quad \text{where } g'(y) = \frac{d}{dy} g(y) \quad ((5))$$

There will also be a term from $i \frac{d}{dt} \exp[i q(y) \frac{d}{dt} b(t)] = - \frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dt} b(t) q(y)$ ((6)), but this is real.

From $-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx}$ in ((3)) an imaginary term occurs:

$$\frac{d}{dx} F = (\frac{d}{dy} F) \frac{1}{g'} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} F = -g'' / (g' * g') \frac{d}{dy} F + (1/g') (1/g') \frac{d}{dy} \frac{d}{dy} F \quad ((6))$$

where $F(x)$ is some function.

Thus:

$$(\exp(-i q \frac{d}{dt} b) \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} [W \exp(i q \frac{d}{dt} b)]) = 2i (\frac{d}{dt} b) q' (\frac{d}{dy} W) / [g' * g'] + 1/(g' * g') \frac{d}{dy} \frac{d}{dy} W - g'' (1/g' * g') \frac{d}{dy} W (1/g') + i W (\frac{d}{dt} b) g'' q' / (g' * g') - W (\frac{d}{dt} b)^2 (q')^2 / g'^2 \quad ((7))$$

The complex terms (assuming $W(y)$ is real) are:

$$(\frac{d}{dt} b) (\frac{d}{dy} W) (1/g') = 2 (\frac{d}{dt} b) q' (\frac{d}{dy} W) / (g' * g') + W (\frac{d}{dt} b) q'' / (g' * g') - W (\frac{d}{dt} b) g'' q' / (g' * g') \quad ((8))$$

If one sets $g' = q'/2$, there is a solution.

Thus, one has an equation in terms of the real function $W(y)$ of the form of the time-independent Schrodinger equation. One may have pieces of the potential of the form $q(y) d(t)$ where $d(t)$ is some function of t . Then:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dt} b(t) = d(t) \quad ((10))$$

This DE may be solved for $b(t)$. (See (4) for an example.)

Obtaining an Equation for $W_1(y)$ where $W(y) = W_0(y)W_1(y)$

One may now attempt to find an equation similar to ((1)) for $W_1(y)$, where $W_0(y)$ is a ground state solution. One obtains:

$$-1/2m [1/(g' * g')] \frac{d}{dy} \frac{d}{dy} W_1 - 1/2m g'' / (g' * g') \frac{d}{dy} W_1 - 1/m (\frac{d}{dy} W_0 / W_0) (1/g' * g') \frac{d}{dy} W_1 \quad ((11))$$

This may then be compared with the hypergeometric equation ((3)). A further transformation $z(y)$ may be necessary to ensure the coefficient of $d/dz \frac{d}{dz} W(z)$ is at most quadratic in z and that of $d/dz W(z)$ linear.

It may be noted that ((11)) contains $d/dy W_0 / W_0$ which is associated with the coefficient of $d/dz W(z)$. Thus, when one equates the coefficient of $d/dz W(z)$ with $az+c$, where a and c are constants, one obtains an equation for $d/dy W_0 / W_0$.

Now:

$$1/(g'g') \frac{d}{dy} \left(\frac{d}{dy} \frac{W_0}{W_0} \right) - 1/(g'g') \left(\frac{d}{dy} \frac{W_0}{W_0} \right)^2 = (E_0 - V(y)) \quad ((12))$$

Thus, knowing $d/dy W_0 / W_0$ as a function of y yields $d/dy \left(\frac{d}{dy} \frac{W_0}{W_0} \right)$ and one may solve for $V(y)$. This yields a potential compatible with a Rodrigues polynomial solution. In general, if $b(t)$ is not vt ($v=\text{constant}$), one might add a term $g(y)d(t)$ to the potential where $d/dt d/dt b(t)=d(t)$.

Example of $g(y)=y = x - b(t)$

This is the example of (3) and (4) to which we apply ((12)). In this case:

$g(y)=y$ and $g'=1$ so:

$$-1/2m \frac{d}{dy} \frac{d}{dy} W_1 - 1/m \frac{d}{dy} W_1 \left(\frac{d}{dy} \frac{W_0}{W_0} \right) = (E - E_0) W_1 \quad ((13))$$

If one leaves the coefficient of $d/dy \frac{d}{dy} W_1$ as a constant, then:

$$\left(\frac{d}{dy} \frac{W_0}{W_0} \right) = ay+c \quad ((14))$$

One may see that this leads to a harmonic oscillator potential.

One may, however, argue that the coefficient of $d/dy \frac{d}{dy} W_1$ should be a quadratic (or even linear). Consider $z=s(y)$, then:

$$\frac{d}{dy} W = \frac{d}{dz} W (z') \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{d}{dy} \frac{d}{dy} W = \frac{d}{dz} \frac{d}{dz} W (z'^2 z'') + \left(\frac{d}{dz} W \right) (z''') \quad ((14))$$

Thus, as an example, one may take the coefficient of $d/dz \frac{d}{dz} W$ as $c_1 c_1 z^2$. Then:

$$z'^2 z'' = z^2 z'' \quad \text{or} \quad z' = c_1 z \quad \text{thus} \quad z = \exp(-c_1 y)$$

One might even obtain a more general result. The exponential, however, leads to a Hulthen type of potential.

Potential Associated with $g(y)=y^2$

Apart from the linear function $g(y)=y$, consider, as an example, $g(y)=y^2$. This does not necessarily lead to a physically important potential, but demonstrates the method.

In such a case, $g'=2y$ and equation ((1)) becomes:

$$(E-E_0) W_1 = -1/2m \left[\frac{1}{(4y^2)} \frac{d}{dy} \frac{d}{dy} W_1 - \frac{.5}{y^2} \frac{d}{dy} W_1 \right] - \frac{1}{m} \left(\frac{d}{dy} \frac{W_0}{W_0} \right) \frac{1}{(4y^2)} \quad ((15))$$

Then: $(z'^2 z') \frac{1}{(4y^2)} = 1$ or $\frac{d}{dy} z = 2y$ and $z = y^2$. Then:

$$(-1/2m) \left(-\frac{1}{(2y^2)} (2y) \right) - \frac{1}{m} \left(\frac{d}{dy} \frac{W_0}{W_0} \right) \left(\frac{2y}{(4y^2)} \right) = az+c = ay^2+c \text{ or}$$

$$\frac{d}{dy} \frac{W_0}{W_0} = -ay^2 - 2cy + 2$$

$$\frac{d}{dy} \left(\frac{d}{dy} \frac{W_0}{W_0} \right) = -3ay - 2c \text{ and:}$$

$$-3ay - 2c - 4y^2 (E_0 - V) = (-ay^2 - 2cy + 2)^2$$

This leads to a polynomial potential with y to the powers of -2,-1,0, 1,2,4.

Alternatively, one may set the coefficient of $\frac{d}{dz} \frac{d}{dz} W_1$ to z i.e.

$$(z'^2 z') \frac{1}{(4y^2)} = z \text{ or } \frac{dz}{z^5} = 4y^2 dy$$

This seems to lead again to polynomials, although the orders will be different

Finally, we consider the coefficient of $\frac{d}{dz} \frac{d}{dz} W_1$ as z^2 ($c_1 z^2 + c_2$ would be more general).
Then:

$$(z'^2 z') \frac{1}{(4y^2)} = A z^2 \text{ or } \ln(z) = Ay^2 \text{ or } z = \exp(Ay^2) \text{ and } z' = 2Ay \exp(Ay^2)$$

$$\text{Then } \frac{d}{dy} \frac{W_0}{W_0} = (2 + 2ya/A + (2cy/A) \exp(-Ay^2)) \text{ and}$$

$$\frac{d}{dy} \left(\frac{d}{dy} \frac{W_0}{W_0} \right) - 4y^2 (E_0 - V) = \left(\frac{d}{dy} \frac{W_0}{W_0} \right)^2 \quad ((16))$$

$$V(y) \text{ is of the form: } C_1 + C_2 \frac{1}{(y^2)} \exp(-Ay^2) + C_3 \frac{1}{(y^2)} + C_4 \exp(-Ay^2) + C_5/y + C_6 \frac{1}{(y)} \exp(-Ay^2) + C_7 \exp(-2Ay^2) \quad ((17))$$

It should be noted that for all of these potentials above:

$y^*y = x - b(t)$. Furthermore, if $b(t)$ is not vt ($v = \text{constant}$), then one may add $y^*y d(t)$ where $d(t)$ could be a periodic function and $d/dt d/dt b(t) = d(t)$. Thus, the wavefunctions and potentials which look time independent actually contain a time component. This, however, is consistent with (3).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to present an approach for converting a time-independent Schrodinger equation into one which has the appearance of a time independent one with the variable x replaced with y where $g(y) = x - b(t)$. We then use $W(y) = W_0(y)W_1(y)$, where $W_0(y)$ is the “ground state” solution, to obtain a DE for $W_1(y)$. We compare this to the general hypergeometric equation ((3)) and try to find potentials $V(y)$ which are compatible, thus ensuring a Rodrigues polynomial solution

References

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